

LABOR MOBILIZATION AND ITS CONSEQUENCES IN THE TURKESTAN REGION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8049460>

ARTICLE INFO

Qabul qilindi: 12-June 2023 yil

Ma'qullandi: 15-June 2023 yil

Nashr qilindi: 17-June 2023 yil

KEY WORDS

Turkestan, Tsarist Russia, labor, volost, village

ABSTRACT

This article discusses the causes and consequences of the 1916 national liberation movement against labor in Turkestan.

The ideas of independence and freedom have been passed from generation to generation as a symbol of the life of the Uzbek people since deep historical times. As it is said, "To love the motherland is from faith", keeping it as the apple of one's eye is considered a sacred duty of every conscientious person. For this reason, the Uzbek people have valiantly fought against the invasions and domination of invaders, valuing independence as the meaning of their lives throughout their many thousand years of history. For example, our ancestors have been fighting for freedom against the invaders who invaded our country since ancient times. As a result of these freedom struggles, the state of our great grandfather Amir Temur was created in our motherland Movorounnahr and flourished socio-economically, politically and culturally and left an indelible mark in history.

President Shavkat Mirziyoyev: "National history should be created with a national spirit. Otherwise, it will not have an educational effect. It is not without reason that we should teach our youth to learn from history and draw conclusions, arm them with the science of history and historical thinking¹.

In the middle of the 19th century, the colonial war started by Tsarist Russia in Central Asia and its transformation into a dependency brought heavy hardships to the peoples of Turkestan.

After Tsarist Russia invaded Turkestan, it spilled the blood of the people, turned the country into a colony of Tsarist Russia, turned the whole life upside down, and violently destroyed the whole life, customs, and cultural foundations of the peoples there. .

The national movements written down in history were not a random event but a product of political and socio-economic life. The similar uprising of 1916 also had its own and suitable ground. It was formed in Turkestan at the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century. According to the conditions, he rose and spread his arms wide. It is

¹ Shavkat Mirziyoyev: Jamiyat hayotining tanasi iqtisodiyot bo'lsa, uning joni va ruhi ma'naviyatdir. <https://president.uz/uz/lists/view/4089>

known that the Russian state established its rule by destroying the nation-state and the political-administrative system by destroying and ruining the entire country. As a result, the local people were deprived of their independence and freedom, and were kept under the yoke of colonial policy and national oppression. In 1867, a military government was established in the country under the name of the Turkestan Governor General. Generals and officers were appointed to high and middle administrative positions. In the same year, von Kaufman was appointed as the first governor-general. The head of the country, who has great powers, played an important role in the establishment of the political-administrative system based on colonialism.

General von Kaufman gave instructions to appoint representatives of the indigenous population to the positions of elders of the volosts and villages. They were only people who obediently executed the tasks of the tsarist administration. The governor general's office was considered the supreme administrator of the country, and regional and uyezds administrations were subordinated to it.

Despite the fact that Turkestan had a lot of natural resources - coal, non-ferrous metals, oil resources - it did not have its own industry. Ordinary iron and tools were brought from Russia and even from abroad. As the industrial products of Russia occupied the markets of Turkestan, the work of local artisans was depressed². In the middle of the 19th century, the colonial war started by Tsarist Russia in Central Asia and its transformation into a dependency brought heavy hardships to the peoples of Turkestan.

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² Xaydarov X. Jizzax tarixidan lavhalar. T. 1992. 19-bet.

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It is noted that the right to exile politically dangerous persons from the country is given to the governor-general. Also, the powers of the military governors of the region were discussed and they were given the right to appoint or dismiss uyezd, precinct bailiffs, police chiefs and senior elders. The regulation of the administration of this country continued with some changes until 1917, that is, until the tsarist government was overthrown.

During the considered period, the country was governed on the basis of four temporary Regulations.

The system of military administration in the country was so important and strong that all gubernias in the country were included in the Ministry of Internal Affairs, while Turkestan was subordinated to the Ministry of War.

The representatives of the regional and uyezd administrations under the Turkestan General Governorship escalated violence and injustice. Provinces are divided into uyezds, and uyezds are divided into volosts. Volosts are made up of rural communities and villages. "Provincial administrations were executive institutions of military governors and directly obeyed them. The rights and duties of the regional administrations were equal to those of the Russian gubernia. The rights and duties of regional administrations were very large. They were engaged in the management of state property, resettlement of settled and nomadic population, performed taxation and revenue collection, led city, uyezd and village administrations, watched over irrigation facilities, they dealt with all issues related to the city and agriculture⁴».

Therefore, the powers of military governors, who are the heads of regions, are extremely diverse and cover all spheres of life. At one time, they were considered commanders of military units in one or another region. The police were also under their control. Thus, almost all representatives of the local upper class were deprived of power and their activities in political life were severely affected. Only a certain part of them were forced to serve in lower administrative positions as agents of the invaders.;

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³ NAUz, fund 1, list 25, case 24. Sheet 109.

⁴ O'zbekiston tarixi. 1 jild, ikkinchi kitob, T.: 2011.-B. 110.